

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: WHAT WILL AMERICA LOOK LIKE POLITICALLY AFTER THE 2020 CENSUS?

Antoinette S. Christophe ,Michael O. Adams, Carroll G. Robinson

Texas Southern University,USA

ABSTRACT

As partisan politics began to wane and realign itself voters are questioning who they are politically. Are they Democratic, Republican, populist nationalist or multicultural globalists? How will they categorize themselves Black, White, Hispanic, or some other race? After the 1928 election there were a precarious changes to the electoral demographic that influenced the 1932 election. The 2016 election is perilous will it too result in an era of Democratic political domination or is the old political system crumbling and a new American political order is being born? Furthermore, how will the evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) impact the status of U. S. politic in 2020? The purpose of this research addresses these important issues that will introduce a vigorous and informed debate going forward in a society where transparency is a requirement mandated by an ever transforming voting body.

KEYWORDS

Artificial, Intelligence, Elections, MogIA, Electoral, Polling, Media

1. INTRODUCTION

Within these United States changes in structure and administration can result in transformative miracles for its Nation. In addition, with the entry and reentry of each presidential candidate the mindset seems to be reorganization is equated to reform and progress. I posed the question is the resolution of deep-seated issues via reorganization only a myth sought after by those who occupy the highest office in this U. S. society? Where then does reality reside? The true may exist that democratic systems still work in response to the needs of all the people inside of the concept of a balance between organizational structure and administrative needs that is not immune to public control; all-encompassing of the less powerful sectors. However, in a space of no agreement, priorities embedded in diverse and conflicting objectives will birth a large amount of existing controversies. The purpose of this research is to compare the presidential elections that took place prior to and during the “Great Depression” (1928-1936) to the present day economic depression or economic short falls (2008-2016). Then to further explore the impact of public control versus artificial intelligence’s influence on presidential election outcomes. The objectives of this research are:

1. Compare the historical account of the two aforementioned era of suppressed economic activities and determine if there is an election patternstrend.
2. Explore if present day elections are being influenced by artificial intelligence (AI), positively or negatively.
3. Ascertain if election pattern via the use of AI can determine what America might look like politically after the 2020 census and the next presidential election.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. PRESIDENTIAL ELECTIONS BEFORE & DURING THE GREAT DEPRESSION (1928-1936)

2.1.1. 1928 Presidential Election

This was a time when Republicans had occupied the presidency for 12 years. The 1928 presidential campaign and election took place in a time of anti-Catholic emotions, Prohibition, and heated conversations concerning civil rights for women and African Americans. Herbert Hoover was the Republican candidate, a Protestant who ambiguously supported Prohibition, but showed certain support for civil rights for women and African American. Contrastingly different, Al Smith, the Democratic nominee, was a Catholic and an anti-Prohibitionist. Both Party's platform was lower taxes, restriction of immigration, the radio broadcast industry regulation and ongoing prosperity that existed in the previous administration (Coolidge).

However, there were differences amongst the two opposing candidates that influenced the outcome of this election. Hoover was a man with a distinguishing Midwestern accent and diction and Smith was perceived as being a New Yorker with flamboyant speech, a derby hat, and a cigar in his mouth. Smith's image didn't mesh well with rural voters. Smith supported proposed grain subsidies (McNary-Haugen Farm Bill) and Hoover had vetoed the bill twice, as secretary of Commerce, under the Coolidge administration. Hoover recanted by vowing to call a special session of Congress to review the issue of farm relief if he was reelected.

The campaign was played out via radio and news bulletins; the first form of primitive artificial intelligence (AI). This new way of reaching the voter-base was used more by Hoover than Smith, possibly allowing more contact with voters by Hoover. As a result of these various factors, Hoover demeanor (rural Midwestern) and ways of being the Republican Party embraced the presidential victory (444 to 87 elected votes). The popular vote was 58.2% for Hoover and 40.8% Smith (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2017).

2.1.2. 1932 Presidential Election

This was the first election held during the United State era of the "Great Depression". The year was 1932 and the American people were suffering ever-increasing hardships. Due to the Nation's desire to escape the deepening economic crisis, a dramatic shift in the political alliance manifested. The Democratic nominee, Franklin D. Roosevelt, started a new trend, appearing in person to accept the candidacy saying, "I pledge you, I pledge myself to a new deal for the American people (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2017)." Hebert Hoover was re-nominated by the Republican Party. As with the previous election (1928), the demeanor of the Republican and Democratic candidate was very different. Roosevelt was genial and confident and Hoover continued to be grim and obstinate.

The American people desperate for change faced a dilemma, choosing between the incumbent, Hoover, who had passed many unsuccessful policies resulting in a depression, or Roosevelt who was vaguely explaining a "New Deal" program. To add to this confusing electoral environment, Hoover was saying external events caused the depression not his leadership and that the "New Deal" Roosevelt was promoting would farther deepen the Nation into an existing economic crisis. Roosevelt recanted that via implementation of the "New Deal" he would use the power of federal government to provide aid to farmers, develop electric power system for the public, balance the budget, put into place oversight of reckless private economic powers, while reducing unemployment with the creation of a vast number of jobs birth out of the "New Deal" legislation. The American people elected Roosevelt casting nearly 23 million popular votes (57.3%) and 472 electoral votes. Hoover received nearly 16 million popular votes (39.6%) and 59 electoral votes.

Furthermore, a substantial number of Democrats were elected to both houses of Congress. After Roosevelt's successful election, up to the time of his inauguration, Hoover tried to reach out to Roosevelt to work on reducing the deepening economic predicament by abandoning 90% of the "New Deal". There was no cooperation from Roosevelt in Hoovers' attempt to derail the "New Deal" and the result was a continued economic decline in an already devastating economic crisis. By March 4, 1933, inauguration day most banks had shutdown, productions in industries were 56% of what it was in 1929, 13 million working American people were unemployed and farmers were suffering at alarming rates(Encyclopedia Britannica, 2017).

Once in office President Roosevelt quickly implemented the "New Deal" to realize economic recovery, to provide assistance to millions of poor, unemployed Americans and to restore facets of the already collapsed U. S. economy. The "New Deal" legislation was passed within the first 100 days of Roosevelt's Presidency and there were evidence of some recovery by the time of the midterm elections (1934). During that same year more Democrats were elected to office and Roosevelt's farther his efforts with the implementation of the "Second New Deal of 1935. This new legislation encompassed the Social Security Act and the Works Progress Administration. During the same midterm election the now Democratic Congress passed a major tax revision that raised the taxes for rich and large corporations.

2.1.3. 1936 Presidential Election

By the time of the 1936 election the Republican Party was devastated over their 1932 defeat, resulting in the party running an anti-Roosevelt/pro-Republican campaign with Alf Landon as their presidential nominee. The Democrats nominated Franklin D. Roosevelt again and he accepted his nomination in person, as he did in 1932. Roosevelt's campaign was supported by farmers, laborers, and the poor. Roosevelt declared "This generation of Americans have rendezvous with destiny (Beckwith, 2017). Landon received fewer than 17 million popular votes (36.5%). While Roosevelt won 27 million popular votes (60.8%) supporting his candidacy, carrying every U.S. state except Maine and Vermont.

2.2. PRESIDENTIAL ELECTIONS DURING PRESENT DAY ECONOMIC SHORT FALLS (2008-2016)

2.2.1 2008 Presidential Election

Two senators were vying for the 2008 Presidential election. Barack Obama was the Democratic presidential candidate and John McCain was the Republican contender. This presidential race was carried out in a climate of financial calamity, the world market was experiencing heavy losses, Americans' retirement was being negatively impacted, the U. S. Government was having to provide emergency loans to American firms and some financial institutions had to file bankruptcy or sale their businesses. The American people was desperate for change. The Bush Administration passed the Emergency Economic Stabilization Act of 2008 to bailout the U. S. financial system with up to 700 billion dollars. This enacted legislation was thought to bring to a standstill a collapsing economy.

This was the first presidential election where artificial intelligence (AI) was paramount. News casting on broadcast networks, the internet, smartphones 24/7 hours around the clock. There was a proliferation of blogs disputing factual and erroneous information. It was via artificial intelligent mechanisms that both presidential candidates tried to control the political conversations in the voting bases. McCain attempted to portray Obama as a naïve, inexperienced celebrity with socialist ideas, willing to sit down and negotiate with anti-American governments. McCain also attacked Obama concerning his association with Bill Ayers and repetitively referring to Ayers as an "unrepentant domestic terrorist" that sit on board with and live blocks away from President Obama. Americans were bombard with internet blog, mass social media, as well as

constant news being streamed on You Tube; all easily accessed on smartphones that most American are perpetually linked to. Based on emails and other AI devices that were identified, many American were starting to believe false accounts that Obama was Muslim even though he was a known practicing Christian.

To level the playing field and counteract inaccurate information Obama, via use of AI, established a website called, "Fight the Smears". The primary purpose of this website was to provide a means to fight back against hateful, vicious and desperate computerized robo-calling and emails. President Obama used AI techniques to cast doubts concerning McCain by tying him at every hand to President George W. Bush (lowest popularity rating of all modern presidents). He stated McCain voted with Bush 90% of the time during his administration. When McCain wanted to suspend his campaign in September 2008 and postpone the first presidential debate to return to Washington D. C. to address the U. S. financial crisis, Obama said, "It's going to be part of the president's job to deal with more than one thing at once." This comment hit the media circuit and streamed on the internet like a wildfire, shading a negative light on McCain's ability to multi-task; a necessary skillset for the CEO of the United States of America. Barak Obama use AI via the use of internet to register million so new voters and to foster amazing passion and enthusiasm around his campaign. Because the millennial generation is computer enthusiast they embrace the chance to tune in with their iPhone and Android smartphones. McCain on the other hand held numerous town hall meeting throughout the country; having face-to-face contact with the voting base. This strategy was up close and personal, but it was impossible to network with as many people as one could touch using AI devices.

Election night Barack Obama had won with 365 electoral votes and 53.9% of the popular vote. McCain won 173 electoral votes (45.7% popular vote). On November 04, 2008 Barack Obama was elected as the 44th president ushering in many first times for the United States. President Obama was a first-term senator instated as CEO of the U.S., the first sitting U. S. senator since John F. Kennedy (1960) that became president, the first African American to become president of these United States of America.

2.3. 2012 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION

In 2012 the country was still struggling economically and the American people remain hopeful that relief would finally come. For this reason, the economy inhabited the center stage of this campaign with two presidential nominee diverging on foreign policy. President Obama was the Democratic candidate, citing withdrawal of U. S. troops from Iraq and killing Osama bin Laden as his triumphs. Mitt Romney, former governor of Massachusetts, was the Republican presidential choice to run. Romney said under the Obama administration and governance the U. S. had lost momentum in global affairs. Furthermore, the two candidates envisioned very different possible futures for the country. Romney proposed tax cuts and to reduce government regulations. In turn, Romney felt that this effort would help small businesses to rebound, prosper, and strengthen the struggling U. S. economy. Romney goals also included repealing Obama's Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (Obamacare) and achieve energy independence with the expansion of domestic energy sources, i.e., offshore oil.

Obama stated his economic strategies helped prevent a full-scale depression and provided an avenue to economic recovery. Similar to the "Great Depression of 1932", President Obama approaches was embodied in the response to the modern day "Great Recession (2007-2009)" and "Financial Crisis of 2008". Liken to the 1932 "New Deal" President Obama proposed to invest in infrastructure, but also including transportation, education, and clean energy.

Both candidates faced challenges. Obama continued to try to recover a struggling economy that he inherited for the previous Bush Administration. Romney while unwilling to offer his tax returns, was crushed by the release of a video where Romney avowed 47% of Americans that

don't pay federal income taxes thought they were victims, but in reality they existed as people that were looking for the government to be responsible for them. Obama responded that Romney was out of touch with middle-class America.

Most of this campaign went viral over the internet, social media, news streamed via You Tube and blogs 24/7. However, at the end of Election Day President Obama was victorious with 332 electoral votes (51.1% popular vote) compared to Romney's 206 electoral votes (47.2% popular vote). Obama carried all the states he carried in 2008, except Indiana and North Carolina.

2.4. 2016 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION

This was a time when many voters bellowed their great desire for change. Few remembered that eight years prior, on the heels of an economic crisis and financial breakdown Obama took charge of the Oval Office in 2008. During his eight years of presidency, with a congressional resistance on ever hand, Obama continually promoted economic expansion, however the bulk of the jobs created were part-time. In addition, many stated that his signature accomplishment, Obamacare, was failing financially. It was an unbridled, abrasive, unleashed 2016 campaign. Trump's anti-Washington demeanor attracted white working-class voters located in states with crucial manufacturing industries or rural Americans. Trump was an outsider, with no political job experience, no political ties, especially no dealings with Washington D. C. "business-as-usual" political model.

During the campaign, Trump broadcasted that it was Democratic Party's establishments that facilitated an environment of costly intervention in foreign conflicts. He believed it was these involvements that drove the widening divide that exist between the upper class and lower class, with ever an increasing, disappearing middle class imminent. Trump also cited that such a divide resulted in stagnant wages and an influx of immigrants freely crossing the borders due to failed enforcement of immigration laws by President Obama. He farther charged that Clinton was an actor in this downfall as Secretary of State. Trump unusual campaign style was filled with negative, abrasive, personal attacks and name calling, i.e. "low energy Bush" (Jeb), "little Marco" (Marco Rubio), and "lying Ted" (Sen. Ted Cruz). He also often ridiculed the national news networks, referring to them as "the most dishonest people that I have ever met." Clinton also

engage in name calling, referring to Trump as a racist, sexist, homophobic, xenophobic, and Islamophobic. This was followed by a release of an unaired tape (2005) from a TV show "*Access Hollywood*" where Trump bragged about taking sexual liberties with women. Trump quickly denied that he had made unwanted advances to women. Then a dozen women spoke out accusing Trump of doing what he had bragged about in the unaired tapes.

Hillary Clinton's claim to fame was the credentials and experience she acquired as Secretary of State. However, many Trump supporters viewed this as the existing corrupt U. S. government establishment. Clinton was very good at organizing and fund-raising and most believed because of her government status quo and ability to raise money that she would be the front-runner and the winner in the presidential election. However, in July 2016, during the democratic primary, artificial intelligence raised its head with the release of nearly 20,000 hacked emails by WikiLeaks indicating that the DNC was favoring Clinton and was ridiculing her top contender, Bernie Sanders, which many millennials supported.

Artificial intelligence ran rampant toward the end of the presidential race:

1. August 2016 – news reports leaked that Trump's second campaign manager, Paul Manafort may have received money from a pro-Russian Ukrainian political party.
2. October 2016 – WikiLeaks release about 50,000 emails from John Podesta account (via a password phishing operator). Federal agents believed Russia was interfering with the U.S. election and that they were WikiLeaks' sources.

3. Late in the campaign, accounts of Clinton's private email server located in her New York home, resurfaced late in the presidential campaign. (While secretary of state, Clinton turned over about 31,000 emails, but ordered about 31,000 emails to be destroyed).
4. FBI Director James Comey wrote a letter to Congress stating that the FBI was reopening the case because they found new email on the laptop of Anthony Weiner (former congressman married to a top Clinton Aide). However, two days before the presidential election Comey concluded that these emails were just duplicates of the ones that had already been investigated. After this event Clinton's lead continued to grind downward.

Once the election ended Republican Donald Trump had lost the popular vote (46.0%) to Clinton (48.1%) by greater than 2.8 million votes, but he had won the electoral vote, 304 votes to Clinton's 227. Trump was elected the 45th President of the United States.

After the election was over the Clinton supports accentuated that Comey reopening the issue concerning Clinton's private email server and the Russian computer hacking from a questionable Internet site was her demise; along with the undemocratic character of the Electoral College. The top administration of 17 U. S. intelligence agencies agreed that Russia, via AI, had engaged in a systematic attempt to bias the election outcome in favor of Donald Trump. An investigation of these allegation have been demanded by the new 2017 Congress.

3. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IMPACT ON 2020 ELECTION PATTERNS: WILL IT SWAY HOW AMERICA LOOKS POLITICALLY POST 2020 CENSUS?

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a discipline where computational technologies/machineries utility is analogous to and mimic how people's nervous system and body sense, learn, reason and take actions. AI systems can be damaging or helpful because the algorithms that drives AI based systems in making decisions using data. These datum inform the AI system and the decision is less biased that that of a typical person. On the other hand, once information (data) is biased the outcome can be discrimination based on race, sexual orientation, political affiliation, or a number of other factors. Moreover, AI-technologies can increase the already existing inequalities when access opportunities is disseminated across society in an unequal, unfair manner. Individual who

are allowed access to AI-systems will experience heighten abilities and efficiencies than those less fortunate; people denied admittance (Stone; et.al, 2016).

Artificial intelligence make machines intelligent. Intelligence is a quality which empowers an individual or entity to function appropriately using environmental forethought. For these reasons, action must be taken to avert AI-based systems from replicating discriminatory behavior, for example, machine learning that identifies targeted groups of people via illegal indicators, i.e., political party affiliation, race, gender or by using highly-correlated surrogate factors, i.e., zip codes, voting precinct. Furthermore, information is being delivered digitally at exponential rates, logging citizen preferences and usage characteristics, voting patterns, political attitude. These datum can be micro-analyzed and ultimately micro-served to specialized segments of the population. Because biases may be introduced to this micro-analysis via biased of the AI designer or user, this is of growing concern. As AI is increasingly assimilated into industrial, consumer, and government devices and products a call for greater control and regulations is needed. Oversight of AI as it applies to "critical infrastructure" is highly important. Under Obama's Presidential Policy Directive (PPD) 21 critical infrastructure is any system or network, physical or virtual that if incapacitated will make ineffective the Nation's security, economy, public health or safety (Stone; et.al, 2016). For example, Google, Facebook, and Amazon continuously lobbied not to be cited as an infrastructure critical to the United States economy. However, as the incorporation of artificial intelligence is increasingly used by those maintaining operation of critical infrastructure, policies and legal consideration may become a sensitive issue that must be

addressed. The more AI applications began implementing and engaging in actions criminal by nature (things that if carried out by humans would equate to crime), the further our judicial, executive, and legislative bodies will be left perplexed as to how to assign accountability to the violators, virtual or human.

Privacy and politics are two other areas that will be affected by this growing trend of AI. An individual's private information stands the chance of being made public through the decisions, predictions and extrapolations of AI algorithms. Citizens' solitude may be a fleeting dream once their lives are permeated by anthropomorphic technology. Present day machines already predict credit risk and recidivism rates using complex algorithms. Artificial intelligence is presently used by politicians to suppress votes, social media platforms use "bots" in a similar manner. Moreover, the way in which an administrator or lawmaker crafts the laws governing AI can determine if democratic participation is promoted or reduced, just by design (Stone; et.al, 2016).

A system referred to as MogIA can use 20 million data points from Google, YouTube and Twitter platforms to predict presidential elections (Steinbuch, 2016; Mohan, 2016). MogIA predicted the past three presidential elections correctly. The unique aspect concerning MogIA is that algorithmic biases are less likely because MogIA learns from its environment, then translates learning into rules at the policy layer and develops an expert system without discarding data. MogIA functions via engagement with tweets and videos, but the system is unable to determine if the post is positive or negative, which makes it hard to gauge actual candidate's support (Engel, 2016). One thing that is clear, AI that MogIA is based on is currently influencing social media interaction. For example, Trump and Clinton, during their campaigns, would dump a gigantic number of tweets in very short periods using MogIA. The outcome was an illusion of a "trending" opinion, conducted by robots (Mohan, 2016). President Obama's campaign (2008 & 2012) used computing power to determine public opinion trends and voter concerns (based on locations and demographics). Using AI—device, like MogIA, to detect trending opinions assist campaigns to be more efficient with time, energy, and resource to be more certain the right message is targeting the correct audiences. Mass communication such as newspapers, radio and television expands getting messages out effectively: positive and negative. However, the speed and magnitude of AI, especially MogIA, is exponential.

4. DISCUSSION & FINDINGS

In this study two eras of economic suppression are compared. The time of the Great Depression (1928 – 1936) and the more recent period of economic shortfalls and decline (2008 – 2016), which was first spearheaded by the previous Bush administration as a result of the Iraq invasion, automotive, bank, and mortgage loan bailouts. The two time periods were selected because of the actions taken by the various stakeholders.

During the Great Depression most campaigns were run via radio and news bulletins. There wasn't real-time coverage of any campaigns and when Roosevelt broke tradition and appeared in person to accept the party's nomination the world took note and were stunned. The candidates traveled and held campaign rallies, shaking hands, kissing babies, and listening to what the citizens' needs were. The race was to win the hearts, souls and votes of the people. In this day and age the electoral votes basically followed the trending lines of the popular votes. News press, radio and television was a tool to increase the ability to reach out to a great portion of the U. S. population, the masses.

Some seven decades later the election platform has transformed into an entity that would be almost unrecognizable to our predecessors. The election goal today is to win the greatest number of electoral votes, by any means necessary. Where the campaigns are more of a reality show than a race to win the hearts, souls and votes of the people. It is not a race where all individual votes are sorted after, instead the votes of the states that will bring the greatest electoral count are considered

premier. With the innovation of computers and artificial intelligence (AI) devices officials desiring to win a spot in office can now gain a winning-edge if they have a command and understanding of deep learning, computer-assisted telephone interviewer (CATI) system, robo-calling, and more recently MogIA. With AI-devices in play, the popular vote doesn't inevitably trend with the electoral vote. AI use computational technologies/machineries that mimic how people's nervous system and body sense, learn, reason and take actions. The problem is AI-based devices can be manipulated because the algorithms that drives AI based systems in making decisions using data. However, if the data is biased or fraudulently introduced the decision made can be skewed to the advantage of person in charge. With the creation of computer servers and emails came email hacking, followed by mass media coverage. All of these strategies and more results in changing the mindset of those that receive these fault message and their voting behavior may be altered from what it may have been if the AI-device did not exist or was control to insure ethical action are in place at all times. However, the MogIA system appear to collect massive amount of data point (i.e., 20 million) autonomously from online platforms (i.e., Google, YouTube, Twitter) and then independently learn from its environment, making rules of its own at the policy layer (Engel, 2017).

Only in five instances did a president win the electoral vote and lose the popular vote and that was in the election years of 1824, 1876, 1888, 2000, and 2016. Three of the five election years are pre-AI age and there are reason for these occurrences other than AI-device usage:

1. 1824 John Quincy Adams (the 1st election trending the popular vote) – The popular vote was new, 18 states chose presidential electors, and six states allowed the state legislatures to pick the presidential electors. No candidate received the obligatory number of votes (131 total) from the Electoral College, so the election was decided by the House of Representatives, not the people.
2. 1876 Rutherford B. Hayes – A very contentious, controversial election. The Democrats (Tilden) had clearly won the popular vote (4,288,546) over the Republicans (Hayes) with 4,034,311 votes. However, it was not certain concerning the electoral vote. Tilden won 184 electoral votes to Hayes 165, with 20 electoral votes uncertain in Florida, Louisiana, South Carolina, and Oregon. The Oregon presidential candidate was determined to be illegal and as a result of the Compromise of 1877 Hayes was awarded the 20 electoral votes and won the presidential election.
3. 1888 Benjamin Harrison – Grover Cleveland won the popular vote due to his anti-positon on the tariff policy and opposition to Civil War pensions, while Harrison supported industry and factory worker to keep tariffs high. Harrison won the electoral vote by $\leq 1\%$ margin and became the president of the U. S.
4. 2000 George W. Bush – this is post AI-device era but the result are still controversial. Al Gore won the popular vote (51%), but due to the controversy of the hanging-chads in election in Florida (Jeb Bush Governor) and the decision by the Supreme Court to stop the recounting of votes and awarding the Florida votes to Bush.
5. 2016 Donald Trump – Turbulent campaign and election, with the both nominees viewed as unfavorable by the general public. The unexpected upset of all elections. Clinton favored by most media outlets won the popular vote, but lost the electoral vote to Trump. In this campaign Trump was known for tweet on Twitter in response to various actions. Email hacking and email destruction associate with Clinton was one strike against her. Another strike was her perceive big government/old government, business as usual persona. But what delivered the greatest blow was the use of AI-devices to keep these and many other negativities ever-present in the thoughts and judgement of the American people. News of the Russian interfering in the U. S. election lends beliefs of AI being at play just below the surface.

When one examine the picture below you will observe that during the Great Depression time period the electoral vote trending matches the trend found in the popular votes, however in the more recent economic suppressed time the electoral vote trends the popular vote until the year 2016. The media, pollsters, American people all forecast and expected Hillary Clinton to win the presidency. Nevertheless, the only one that made the correct prediction, long before the American citizen went to the ballot box to cast their vote, was the AI-device, MogIA.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Artificial intelligence is a player in the all elections, including the presidential election. With the capabilities embodied in these entities, it behooves mankind to respectfully gain a control of this virtual being. If regulated and overseen the use of AI-devices will be an asset, however the potential remains for the ill-operation of these AI-devices for personal gain. MogIA should be categorized as “critical infrastructure” and place under tight security. MogIA and other AI-device can and will be detrimental to the United States economy, security, federal organizations. Government officials should work toward passing legislation and regulations to administrate and manage these AI-devices, placing harsh penalties on those that are found to be in violation of illegal operation of these technologies and machines for personal gain or to undermine operations directly or indirectly interfaced with critical infrastructure in the U. S. and globally.

REFERENCES

- [1] Beckwith, David C. (2017). “U. S. Presidential Election of 2016” Encyclopedia Britannica, Inc.2017. Web. 13 Feb. 2017 Encyclopedia Britannica Online. (2017). <https://www.britannica.com>
- [2] Engel, Pamela. (2016, Oct. 28). An artificial intelligence system that correctly predicted the last 3 elections says Trump will win. Business Insider. Retrieved from <http://www.businessinsider.com/artificial-intelligence-trump-win-2016-10>
- [3] Mohan, C. Raja. (2016, Nov. 8). Raja Mandala: Artificial Intelligence, real politics. The Indian Express. Retrieved from <http://www.theindiaexpress.com>

- [4] Munro, Andre. (2017). "United States Presidential Election of 2012" Encyclopedia Britannica, Inc. 2017. Web. 13 Feb. 2017
- [5] Polhemus, Lindsie. (n.d.) Artificial Intelligence & Politics. OMNI. Retrieved from <https://omni.media/artificial-intelligence-and-politics>
- [6] Seidman, Harold. (1998). Politics, Position, and Power: The Dynamics of Federal Organizations, 5th Ed. New York: Oxford University Press
- [7] Steinbuch, Yaron. (2016, Oct. 28). Reliable AI system predicts Trump will win. New York Post. Retrieved from <http://www.newyorkpost.com>
- [8] Stone, Peter, et.al. (2016). "Artificial Intelligence and Life in 2030: Report of the 2015 Study Panel"